

EFFECT OF THE STYLISTIC MEANS IN THE SHORT STORIES(ON THE EXAMPLE OF SHORT STORIES BY P SHYUT)**F.Tillahodjayeva.***Kokander PH, lecturer*

Abstract: *For our students to become proficient readers, they need training (especially at the lower levels of proficiency) to develop effective reading strategies. This article highlights the issue of the use of stylistic devices as the growing influence of the authors of works on readers. As an example, the stories of a German writer Peter Schutt has been analyzed.*

Keywords: *stylistic facilities, the impact of the text , the reader , stories, increasing use.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье освещается вопрос использования стилистических средств в качестве усиления влияния авторами художественных произведений на читателей. В качестве примера, делается анализ рассказов немецкого писателя Петера Шюта.*

Ключевые слова: *стилистические средства, влияние, текст, читатель, рассказы, усиление, использовать, значение.*

Every author consciously chooses his or her linguistic means in order to achieve a special effect on the reader. The listing of linguistic means only makes sense if one also goes into the effect that the author is pursuing with them.

Some stylistic devices have the effect that a text appears particularly haunting, the text message is intensified.

The author's appeal is particularly emphasized (urgently) and intensified through the use of anaphor, ellipse, paranthesis, synonyms, and comparisons. He vividly describes his lament (his hope, his hatred, anger) by using various rhetorical means. The argument works through ...

The author wants what he is saying to be particularly clear and comprehensible for the reader, and he dresses his statements in graphic forms of speech: aus der Patsche helfen, sich die Butter vom Brot nehmen lassen in die Tüte kommen, in die Quere kommen.

The author often uses unusual images and image structures in order to make his statement alienating and surprising. It wants to appeal to active and educated readers and cast a spell over them in an aesthetic and vivid way.

The author wants to establish contact with the reader, address him communicatively, and involve the recipient.

"Sie wissen, was ich meine. "Allusion: Anspielung "Ihre Fahrkarte bitte, Gnädige Frau!» Anrede, Apostrophe "Oh ihr Götter! Ausruf, Emphase "Ist das nicht toll?"

Rhetorische Frage «Eines Abends im Frühling - ich hatte gerade mein Abitur bestanden – schlich sie sich davon. Parenthese: Einschub The effect of the stylistic devices is usually a special emphasis that the reader or listener unconsciously picks up. While most stylistic devices are intentionally incorporated into speeches or written works, some are commonplace, for example the ellipse.

However, in order to be able to record a short story correctly, it is important not only to correctly recognize the stylistic device, but also to evaluate it plausibly or to interpret it. The following procedure is always recommended to describe a stylistic device:

1. Correctly quote the passage found.

2. Name the stylistic device ("This is an anaphor.") describe the effect of the stylistic device on the reader ("Induces subliminal pity, reinforces the message, increases urgency.

Particularly when it comes to the interpretation of short stories, stylistic means have to be found, interpreted and evaluated with regard to their effect on the reader.

Stylistic means are all used consciously and are usually intended to make things clearer...

Many stylistic devices are "hidden" in Peter Schütt's short stories.

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Here are words like "spit" for "saliva", "rummaging" for "looking for"

In the short story "Dog and Cat" the ellipses are used:

«Die Evangelischen essen richtige Bohnen, die Katholiken (essen) lieber Pferdebohnen.»

«...die Evangelischen haben Hunde, die Katholischen (haben) Katzen to imitate everyday language. Ellipses can also make the text read faster, for example to convey a hectic pace (great hurry).

Also the following anaphor:

“Die Evangelischen sind ehrlich. Katholiken sind falsch.

Die Evangelischen essen alle Tage Kartoffeln. Katholiken kennen bloß Nudeln und Reis.”

serve to structure and rhythmize texts. Individual parts of the sentence are repeated, reinforcing the message and increasing the urgency. The repeated units are emphasized as particularly significant.

What is most important is a logical justification and interpretation or Effect of the stylistic device - if we have revealed a conspicuous text passage as corresponding, several questions arise that can help as an orientation in an interpretation (or interpretation) and analysis (or determination, investigation) of the stylistic devices:

- Why did the author use exactly this stylistic device at this point?
- Does the use of this rhetorical device have a special meaning?
- What is the core message, the message of the rhetorical style figures?
- How does this stylistic device affect the reader? (very important!)
- Which “rhetorical devices” are used most often?
- In which section of the text are there noticeably many stylistic figures?
- What other anomalies and remarkable stylistic means are noteworthy?

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